

Diplomacy and environment; conflict of interest or need for a legal regime?

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Abstract. Today, environmental protection and sustainable development are two fundamental pillars of human existence. In this process, the major roles are played by governments and international organizations. Adherence to international obligations (Erga Omnes) and Jus Cogens are two important rudiments in environmental diplomacy towards sustainable development. Surely, sustainability in development and Environmental protection would not have happened without serious regional interactions and international cooperation. In addition, sustainable development and development sustainability are not on their accurate path except in international interactions and global peace. Along that, environmental diplomacy is known as an effective method to natural resources and ecosystems conservation. So, environmental discussions are very much important international convergence reason. Therefore, international community can lead to global environmental conservation strategies with that convergence attitude. This research aims to determine the international environmental law evolution firstly and government's roles in front of environmental challenges lying international convergence and legal fundamentals. So, environmental threats and hazards, display an illogical human act, that can be solved under the shadow of international convergence and moving to environmental conservation and global peace.

Keywords. environmental Diplomacy, environmental protection, common obligations and international convergence, international environmental law, sustainable development, international responsibility

1 INTRODUCTION

The discourse of environmental human rights of today is rooted in solidarity rights and international interactions. The right to the environment, biological variation, pollutions, climatic changes, global warming, failing to achieve sustainable development, water crisis, retrogression of beaches and territorial integrity of countries, drought and food security, tension over energy resources, and environmental emigrants, are the most important global environmental challenges acknowledged by defenders of both political and civil rights and natural recourses protection. Like any type of system, the international system is not stationary, but ever changing. International law, which governs the international community, has accordingly gone through many changes and alterations. This is because the very nature of International law is evolutionary. International interactions are effected by legitimacy and legality; however, this is necessary but not sufficient since legitimate interactions need to be balanced and work within a framework of peace. This is achieved only systematically through diplomacy. In any case, protecting the environment is recognized as one of the primary factors in

international community, and international environment as an important current issue in the world. All countries have realized the seriousness of environmental problems and are putting their attempts in protecting their natural environment against any harm and destruction. One influential approach in this regard is extending and reinforcing international relations in the light of diplomacy. Solidarity efforts in this regard brings international convergence. This is a path that ensures environmental protection and facilitates resolving environmental hazards. International convergence has various dimensions such as political, economic, security, social, attitudinal and/or combinatorial. While governments might find the sole answer to environmental protection in convergence, this can only be achieved by means of a successful green diplomacy. This is why convergence is taken into account within the context of environmental international diplomacy.

2 Developing foundations of International Environmental Law

A: the concept of international environmental law

According to literature, there is a relationship between right to the environment, international law, and international environmental law. The development of international law, and the expansion of its application, has been a result of the development of concepts such as human rights, which is the cause that international rules regarding governments' direct and immediate benefits have extended to international and solidarity benefits. Therefore, a preoccupation with human rights is the incentive to these rules. (Molaei, 2009:337)

History shows that after World War I and World War II, human rights initiated international rules, which included gratuitous obligations observing solidarity benefits. With the emergence of new issues such as exploiting aerospace, common heritage of humanity, and environment, these rules gained significant importance within the international system. The ultimate goal of environmental international rules is not the immediate benefits of governments; rather it is the common benefits of humans and the improvement of their future. Therefore, by announcing that humans have the right to a healthy environment, the Stockholm Declaration on Human Environment in 1972 established a fundamental connection between environmental connection and human rights, and initiated new developments in the realm of international law. (EftekharJahromi, 2009:42)

Under this declaration, humans are officially responsible for protecting and improving environment for current and future generations, and the right to healthy environment has ever since the date, been continuously confirmed in different international documents. It is, therefore, necessary to study environmental issues in partnership with all related citizens at a desirable level. At the national level, every individual should have access to all the environmental information possessed by public authorities, such as dangerous materials and activities in the region, and should participate in making

decisions. (Vakil, 2009: 263)

Most environmental activists argue for a specific environmental right based on basic human needs for clean air, clean water, a stable climatic system, and generally an environment leading to human health and living. This shows the emphasis on the interaction of human with environment and governments with their citizens for maintaining a healthy environment. This is the public national diplomacy with roots in culture, history, society, and economics.

B: the methodology of international environmental law

Legal mechanisms working within a context of rules and regulations always underlie systematic cooperation at regional, international, and global levels. Hence, in the framework of international treaty rules, regulated criteria are examined which form legal foundations in different countries. Soft/non-binding rules and hard/binding rules are then set according to different roles. This is observable in all fields including environmental studies. Different definitions have been proposed in this regard. International environmental law, as a set of international customary and arbitrary rules, is one of the newest and most widespread branches of public international law, which has been developed to regulate the relations of adherers to international law in the field of environmental protection (Poor Hashemi and Arghand, 2013:26). This is an area of expertise that is consisted of many other professional ones. Identifying the rules and legal frameworks could serve as a rich research area in this field. Moreover, studying ways of enacting such legal frameworks based on international documents is very important and, the analysis methodology applied on the content of legal frameworks plays a significant role for this purpose (Tayebi, 2015:31).

C: convergence

Convergence is a process through which different units voluntarily give up enforcing individual power to achieve solidarity goals, and instead, they obey an ultra-national authority; separate national units controlled by a government are encouraged to devote their loyalty, activities, and expectations to a new center whose institutions are qualified or require qualification to cover them. Convergence can exist in different areas. For environmental purposes it serves to achieve environmental protection, or to build up an active and dynamic environment (Hassanan, 2013:11)

D: types of convergence

1. Political convergence

This type of convergence is related to collective work for the purpose of improving mutual benefits. Convergence in policies means coordinated acting of a group of

countries. The extent of collaboration and integrity signifies the level of convergence in politics and environment (Hassanan, 2013:4).

2. Social convergence

For the most part, development of social communications depends on the realization of convergence. Some like Carl Deutsch believe that development of social interactions is influential in creating mutual identification, a feeling of common benefits, and a feeling of being one community.

3. Economic convergence

Here, convergence is a model for economic development regarding environment and its protection. Green technologies and tourism are two areas of interest in the theory of economic convergence.

4. Attitudinal convergence

Understanding the common identification of nations and enhancing mutual commitment are discussed under attitudinal convergence. The focus is on creating and reinforcing common feelings and benefits among environmental units in countries and the extent of convergence is determined by what both the elite and the common people (culture) think. (Clark and Pyne, 1987:59)

3 International Obligations and responsibilities for Environmental Protection

A: governments' obligation to protect the environment

Governments' obligation to protect the environment is the obligation to prevent pollution in areas not under their authority. Governments should encourage public sensitivity and participation by informing people. Effective access to jurisdictional and official authorities, and handling jurisdictional and official affairs such as punishment and compensation must be assured. Planning and legislation are two ways by which governments can succeed in fulfilling their objectives concerning environment. The existence of a systematic framework for environmental protection, as well as common binding assurances imply multidirectional interaction, which is called multidirectional environmental diplomacy. In this regard citizens can benefit from the right to healthy environment. However, the primary requirement of this right is having sufficient environmental information. The environmental information that a government has to provide includes: full reports on air, soil, water, vegetation, and animals status, natural sites, harmful activities that can negatively affect these elements, and also, all

environmental protection activities like official arrangements and environmental management plans. This information should be provided in all possible forms including written, visual, auditory, or data bank. Governments are required to share with public all national and international documents regarding environment – strategies, plans, and reports on how they are applied. Governments are also required to publish resolutions and statements of international conferences in the native language of their citizens, especially, when they are about mechanisms elucidating applicants' rights regarding environmental information or their participation in environmental affairs. (Firouzi, 2005: 58)

B: the international responsibility of governments

The international responsibility regarding environmental damage is a legal concept that is defined according to effective international relations based on official diplomacy and the principle of states sovereignty. According to this principle, governments are free to use the natural resources of their land to the extent that it does not interfere with similar rights of other states. Therefore, the principle of states sovereignty assures independent utilizing of one's natural resources without disturbing that of others. If a state activity results in environmental damage, or the risk of such damage, beyond the state borders, the government is held accountable. In order to solve this problem, a number of concepts have been developed under international law; however, when applied to specific cases, none is able to resolve conflicts. In practice, it is difficult to assign responsibility when it comes to environmental issues. This is because the damage is either non-significant, or, the rules regarding strict liability or liability arising from errors have not yet been fully realized internationally. (Poor Hashemi and Arghand, 2013:71)

4 Convergence and environmental cooperation

A: regional convergence

The theory of regional convergence centers on cooperation for achieving a common goal. Convergence here implies a condition of closeness among social, cultural, economic, political and communication organizations and different systems so that they have substituted a new system for previous systems of operation. (Integration of Political Communities, 1971:36)

Regional convergence is viewed from three different perspectives:

- Central powerful countries are very influential
- Influential countries in the region mostly play peripheral roles regarding

international environmental law

- The participation of regional influential countries is very important

B: international convergence in environmental law

International environmental law includes many international treaties, binding resolutions of international organizations, and other non-binding but important statements and resolutions.

The number of international treaties have increased significantly after 70s. Today there are more than 300 treaties (yet, not including the bilateral ones) which in whole or part consider environmental issues. There are also binding treaties (hard law), which are issued under the authority of international organizations, and non-binding ones (soft law). The number of the latter is very large, since all organizations or international conferences can issue this type of treaty (Hassanan, 2013:29). According to the content, treaties are divided into three types: recommendation treaties including instructions for member states as reminders of how to fulfill obligations; declarations of principles which outline the principles, establish new international rules, and need to be included in binding treaties; and action plans which determine what needs to be done. Among declarations of principles, the Stockholm Declaration is the most complete and the most fundamental one on international environmental law and most organizations initiated their major activities adapting its principles. In fact, the Stockholm conference on human and biosphere, whose codification began during the 50s and became global with a large number of countries attending the conference in 1972, is the most important international conference on environment and a turning point regarding its issues. It consisted the foundation of a flexible continuous program titled "United Nations Environment Programme for the environment". This is the most important achievement of the conference and the coordinator of all environmental activities with the aim of protecting and providing human environment and assuring human right to healthy environment, as well as encouraging governments and international organizations to cooperate in controlling pollution as a result of human activities and developing international laws for compensating for damage caused by that pollution and damage at state boundaries and common areas. (Shelton and Kiss, translated by M. Abdollahi, 2010,131)

C: international convergence and environmental protection

1) Regional convergence and environmental protection

In the context of environmental protection, international convergence focuses on establishing peace and improving the international status of environment. In this way, environmental international convergence conflicts with transnational versions of

convergence and is considered an inter-governmental process. In other words, there is more conformity between inter-state approach and regionalism in environmental international convergence.

2) The role of convergence in international environmental protection

With regard to important environmental issues, useful interactions within the available frameworks and considering political, economic, and social aspects underlie convergence at international level. International convergence gives ground to international peace and security and especially guarantees biological security. In this regard, regional convergence experiences can illuminate the way towards global convergence. International environmental protection is achievable in the light of international convergence and green diplomacy.

5 Convergence and environmental cooperation

A: security and lack of integration

Since international convergence can be a commixture of various environmental perspectives, the infrastructure of unity and integration among countries is still weak and fragile. The diversity of institutions, the diplomatic arrangement of convergence, and the multiplicity of actors and authorities in countries are major reasons of the lack of international convergence. Another challenge in the way is the relations between some powerful countries and other transnational powers. Yet, another problem arises from common defense among countries; as of today, there is still no relationship between political and military unity. In this regard defensive diplomacy is at work, which is called defensive and environmental diplomacy.

1) Major obstacles in international convergence

a. Lack of cultural unity

b. Political disputes and reluctance to surrender national sovereignty

c. Economic obstacles (business, tourism, technology) (SeifZadeh, 1990:238)

2) Today, it is clear to all that environmental law is increasingly gaining an international dimension, and has become a powerful factor in the fundamental evolution of international law. It is no doubt that nowadays environmental issues such as protection, development, and so on are the most important instances of international convergence and are studied in the context of human rights. In less than a quarter of a

century, a huge amount of international documents concerning environmental protection have been issued. A major part of these documents considers protection in certain areas like: seas, freshwater, barley, biodiversity, etc. (Kiss et al, translated by Habibi, 2010, v. 1)

B: convergence, a necessity

The necessity of environmental protection is a complicated problem in international law, and different factors are involved in internationalization of this protection. One group of factors are borderless and are integrated into different elements consisting the environment; these are water, air, animals, etc. Another group is accidents such as Kuwait's oil wells and Chernobyl nuclear disasters which are not limited to Kuwait or Russia borders. Fighting with desertification, protecting the Ozone layer, acid rains, etc. are certainly international, and even global, matters considering advancements in human knowledge of the environment and biosphere. Today, what requires international convergence and integration, and highlights the need for similar or common laws, is the problem of pollution in the world. In order to prevent any type of environmental pollution, international communities need to cooperate, and countries with strict regulations should move towards those with more flexible ones.

C: problems in administering convergence in international environmental law

Some of the problems in international interactions are a result of the following:

- National sovereignty. Governments never risk their national benefits against each other. Even in some cases, the internal laws of a country have deficiencies in supporting this matter. Because of this sovereign power international laws cannot be practiced efficiently.
- The other side of the available implementation mechanisms is sometimes forced to hold back because of the force imposed by governments. (Kiss et al, translated by Habibi, 2010, v. 1)
- The lack of mechanisms at work at the national level, such as: executive power, administrative police, or compulsory adjudication in the international community
- The lack of firm performance bonds such as penal punishment against environmental crimes. (Hassanan, 2013:65)
- The lack of an international judicial organ despite the efforts being made in settling environmental disputes in judicial bodies at international level. (Keck Dean et

al, translated by Habibi, 2004, v. 2)

6 Environmental diplomacy; International Interaction and Sustainable Peace

In 1968 United Nations and two other regional organizations (Council of Europe and African Union) passed a number of international documents about environmental protection:

- Declaration on fighting air pollution (March 8, 1968)
- The European charter on water (May 6, 1968)
- Protecting nature and natural resources (September 15, 1968); successor of London convention, 1933
- Stockholm conference
- World Charter for Nature (United Nations)
- Rio conference
- Action Plan for the 21st Century (Agenda 21)

In its short life of about 20 years, international environmental law has seen a huge amount of international documents issued for the protection of our planet's environment. More than 900 bidirectional treaties, 300 multidirectional treaties, and more than 200 ratified documents by international organizations, all encompass more than 3000 rules and regulations for environmental protection. It is worth reminding that the convergence of rights of current and future generations is a serious issue in environmental protection; this convergence can bring human welfare for future generations. (Robinson and Kurukulasooriya, translated by Hosseini, 2011,76)

A: environmental diplomacy, the turning point of global convergence

Negotiation has long been the axis of human interactions at national, regional, and international level. Formal interactions move along the path of diplomacy. Relations are depicted as bi- or multi-directional. One of the issues that has always been a topic of discussion and has recently been the center of attention in the international community is environmental diplomacy. Environmental risks has introduced a lot of

concerns in the international community. These risks, even if small, has sometimes become widespread and taken regional and international dimensions. Although they have increasingly been noticed by the international community, violating international standards and obligations has resulted in many environmental perils. The present study mainly discusses the overall diplomacy and the process of international negotiations towards forming conferences and treaties; however, it is important to note that the aim of environmental diplomacy is to prevent environmental problems. In this process, maintaining a green viewpoint by experts in the area and related authorities can keep the hope of having a safe biosphere. (Tayebi and Mirtorabi, 2014:3)

B: environmental diplomacy and common obligations

Environmental concerns should not cause ignorance of international community obligations, whether for developing or developed countries. Environment should be viewed from an appropriate perspective in either of these countries. Deterioration of environment continues to exist despite many international environmental agreements, and new challenges always show up. The question is: while there are so many approaches to international environmental law, why has the global situation of environment become worse? This is because of many complicated reasons; below is a number of key points that is worth mentioning in this regard.

It seems part of the problem is because of the abundant number of international documents and conventions. There are so many diverse environmental agreements that one might ask if it is possible that the physical and organizational capacity of countries is insufficient for administering them. This diversity increases the potential of interference of regulations, incompatibility of obligations, significant gaps in coverage, and redundancy in objectives and responsibilities. International environmental law has developed in a step by step manner, rather circumstantially, and thus, the scattered shape of the related documents has negatively affected their implementation. (Tayebi, 2013 (1): 2)

Therefore, it is clear that if new environmental challenges occur, we need to think carefully whether we need new laws and institutions, or we need to use appropriate mechanisms for existing laws, or we need to adapt our existing mechanisms to new challenges.

Part of the failure of international environmental law in confronting global environmental challenges is due to the fact that during the development of international environmental law, the effectiveness of this new section has not been considered adequately. However, in recent years, this matter has come to much attention in scientific and political literature, whether generally or in certain systems for specific problems. The most comprehensive study until now, conducted by lawyers and sociologists, and especially scientists of international affairs, has transformed the

specific expressions of international environmental law more than ever.

There are a number of effective factors that lead to novel solutions. The first is the measurement of the influence of a treaty based on its functional data in comparison with its objectives. The second is the influence of abundant legal analysis about why countries follow international regulations despite the lack of severe punishment and effective performance bonds. Finally, the third factor is that modern treaties have different internal systems which allow the involved parties to examine the status of the treaty through scientific mechanisms. (Kraft,2015: 289)

The efficacy of international environmental law against newfound environmental challenges depends mostly on us to escape from the harmful effects of sovereignty on international law. We can imagine that international relations, politics, and law are formed by only one nation, however, obviously one nation cannot solve peripheral environmental problems; rather, it is necessary to have fruitful international interactions through clearly defined paths which can be called environmental diplomacy.

Such advancements create challenges for international law, while also chances for reinforcing and expanding its fundamentals. International law must function within a new multilayer system of countries, international bodies, independent organizational networks of private sections, a wide collection of formal international organizations, the new pattern of unofficial coalitions, and individual innovations. Developing countries, and especially small island ones, are currently facing big challenges regarding pollution. Nevertheless, taking a reaction against existing environmental challenges like pollution is complicated by newfound challenges resulting from climate change. (Tayebi, 2013 (2): 2)

There is not a more effective solution than international interactions plus obligations, with a focus on adaptation requirements, for environmental challenges cause by climate change. Climate change may result in the drowning of many lands. This harmful effect is called “the phenomenon of drowning nations”. Regarding this, a wider range of international efforts is needed. Environmental international communities should act more effectively in making decisions and discussing the problems through environmental diplomacy. (Ranjbarian and Arghandeh Poor, 2012:83)

Other more serious key challenges include keeping biological diversity. An analysis of this critical issue indicates that biodiversity is in danger because of economic measures and institutional reforms. This is another environmental problem for which environmental diplomacy seems to have an answer.

Precise analysis of the role of people’s participation and their access to information in achieving sustainable development and good management of the environment is another issue in today’s environmental discussions. The close relationship between

sustainable development and clarity through accessibility to information is influential in achieving desirable environmental goals. In this regard, the relationship between human rights and environmental protection, specifically rights of nations, is very important. The general right to the environment is one of the most important bases of international environmental law and a structural foundation of environmental and human rights discourse. This is where international relations come to help, and regional, international, and global cooperation plays its role. Realized officially or publicly, it is the specific viewpoint towards environmental international interactions that is shaped by environmental diplomacy. (Larry and Pisupati, translated by Tayebi, 2014:176)

C: Environmental Diplomacy and sustainable development

In national, regional, and international crises, aggressive behavior has created calamities. This can be a serious threat to physical, psychological, environmental, and social health. International interactions can counteract violence, especially green violence and extremism. Serious actions in this regard can take place within the framework of environmental diplomacy. The consequence is continuous international cooperation and stable security, with regard for common international obligations, environmental protection, and human right to a healthy environment.

Sustainable development is achieved through unconditional protection of the environment and natural resources with the aim of conserving common human legacy. In Globalization or internalization, development is important; however, development must be accompanied by sustainability. Without sustainability, development can negatively affect the globalization process and will result in worldwide crisis. In other words, development without sustainability will destroy the biosphere. This is not an advertisement. Even today, the world's environment is not in a good condition and is facing serious problems such as climate change. Therefore, sustainable environment and globalization are in the same direction. It is better to think green while thinking global. (Tayebi, 2013 (2): 3)

7 The future of international environmental law in the Age of Globalization

The future of international environmental law is closely related to the future of environmental global governance. The focus should be on ways of improvement through advancing towards the desirable environmental governance, even if it is constantly being evaluated. This improvement encompasses many dimensions. One is the "plurality of treaties". As mentioned previously, there are serious concerns about this plurality and its effects on the ability of different countries to respond to the increasing environmental challenges. These concerns are more observable in developing, especially small island countries. This means that instead of seeing the new rules set by single nation countries as the last game to be played, we should focus on the most effective ways of facing the existing environmental challenges. This demands

looking beyond the law as the only possible solution to international environmental problems.(Koivurova, translate:Tayebi,2014: 301)

The response of the future of international environmental law (and more generally the global environmental governance) to the new and existing environmental challenges is a necessity which consists a multidimensional evolutionary process. It will use the existing mechanisms, improve them, or even innovate completely novel methods for solving the problems. The future of international environmental law (as part of the global environmental governance) will be an ever changing phenomenon, just like the global environment itself. (Tayebi, 2013 (1): 1).

8 Conclusion

Discussion

Environmental protection and the problem of resources that should be conserved for future generations is one of the century's most important issues. The study discussed international convergence for environmental protection, with an emphasis on the existing problems (legal, political, economic, and social), variables, and other factors such as governmental policies, etc. Environmental protection calls for deeper contemplation on resource productivity. In order to achieve international convergence, there should be rules that can be applied by all countries. Regarding environmental protection, every country should share its expertise, and keep in unity with others. Taking all the above into consideration, it is possible to use the environment more efficiently and decrease the extent of harm and deterioration.

Conclusion

A serious regard for environmental protection by international communities can provide them a chance to balance their foreign affairs through diplomacy, and bolster each other's power of facing environmental phenomena. It should be reminded that one of the most important objectives is to create some kind of balance in international relations, to diversify, and to use the environment properly. Therefore, environmental protection and international convergence do not imply ignoring the weak countries. Certainly, maintaining these relations requires the development of modern and clean technologies in all countries. Convergence should be so that all the world could act in a unified manner, and benefit from the existing technologies. Accordingly, we cannot ignore the role of environmental diplomacy, since the development of international environmental law is indebted to that and positive convergence. It seems the only way to overcome environmental problems is convergence and constant international cooperation. In this respect, environmental diplomacy is one of the basic effective ways of interaction between countries and people, and can ultimately reinforce peace and friendship. Environmental diplomacy is a substantial framework for global

environmental protection and sustainable development. It fortifies human life on the biosphere. International cooperation should be towards development, with an emphasis on the protection of resources and common human legacy. However, every country is expected to adhere to international agreements if the current situation of the world is expected to change. According to the above, it seems environmental diplomacy is one the most effective strategies for protection and sustainable development in the biosphere.

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